

Linguistic data for Livonian

Version 1

Description

Data plan describes data management for data collected and created for Livonian within State Research programme (Latvia) "Latvian Studies for the Development of a Latvian and European Society" project "Multifunctional dictionary of Livonian" (VPP-LETONIKA-2021/2-0002). It contains lexical data for Livonian with meanings provided in Latvian, Estonian and English, as well morphology data and pronunciation examples.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

State Research programme (Latvia) "Latvian Studies for the Development of a Latvian and European Society" project "Multifunctional dictionary of Livonian" (VPP-LETONIKA-2021/2-0002)

Researchers

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Kūla

Organizations

University of Latvia Livonian Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Linguistic data for Livonian

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: State Research programme (Latvia) "Latvian Studies for the Development of a Latvian and European Society" project "Multifunctional dictionary of Livonian" (VPP-LETONIKA-2021/2-0002)

Project: Multifunctional dictionary of Livonian

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Linguistic data for Livonian

Data collection contains lexical data for Livonian with meanings provided in Latvian, Estonian and English, as well morphology data and pronunciation examples. Data is collected as part of the State Research programme (Latvia) "Latvian Studies for the Development of a Latvian and European Society" project "Multifunctional dictionary of Livonian" (VPP-LETONIKA-2021/2-0002).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- JSON

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There was no usable previous data sets existing.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers, developers, community.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Through the registration.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV repository

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Valts Ernštreits (0000-0002-5323-8536)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Sensitive information may be included.

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Privacy constraints
- Privacy policies

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